

INNOVATION AND UZBEKISTAN

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Innovations and scientific and technical processes play an important role in the development of the state. According to the requirements of the order, innovative activity means "the conversion of the results of scientific research and research (innovation) or other scientific and technical achievements into a new or updated product, as well as new or a process that envisages following an updated technological process" is understood.

The state acts as a separate business entity (investor) in the implementation of innovative initiatives. Innovations produced by the state in the implementation of its innovation policy also affect the investment center. The share of development investments in the modern industrial complex is about 45% of the national income. The state supports the innovative development of science for the following reasons:

1. Innovation helps increase wealth. High-quality products are produced, the number of products produced increases at the same time. Innovation affects the competitiveness of an individual or organization.
2. The need to support large-scale and expensive projects, for which companies do not have enough funds.
3. Carrying out scientific and research works in places where there is no share of state property (ecology, medicine, social spheres, construction of wastewater treatment facilities);
4. To carry out scientific and research work of military significance in the field of studying space technologies.

Innovation, at the same time, helps improve the quality of life and increase social diversity, which reduces the harmful environmental impact.

In our country, great attention is paid to innovation, innovative and scientific-research works. President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, who announced the establishment of a scientific-practical center for the implementation of innovations in the student town in Tashkent, said: "Our most important task is to create an environment of innovation in the worldview of our people. Without innovation, there will be no competition and development in any field. Death in this field "If we do not spread the changes widely to our people, if we do not develop skills in people, we will not be able to keep pace with the intensity of today's era and the unprecedented achievements of science and technology".

Innovations are the result of years of hard work. But often, it is more difficult to absorb innovation than to create it. President Shavkat Mirziyoyev signed the decree "On the establishment of the Ministry of Innovative Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan" in 2018 in order to turn on the "green light" for innovations in Uzbekistan. The tasks of the new ministry are to promote promising achievements of scientific research and innovation activities in the country, to develop effective mechanisms in this regard, to strengthen specialized scientific and experimental laboratories, high-tech centers, technological parks and other innovative structures. For example, the goal is derived from human needs. So, through innovative ideas, we can achieve values not today, but sooner, tomorrow.

The Ministry of Innovative Development, which was established almost 5 years ago, will continue its activities as an Innovative Development Agency from January 1, 2023.

So what has been done over the years? What were the results? What has changed and what should be paid attention to again? How has our country developed in terms of innovation over the past 5 years? Who will give a true assessment of this?

Nazokat Abdukunduzova, press secretary of the Ministry of Innovative Development, said these sentences about this in her interview:

"I have been the press secretary of this office since the establishment of the Kamina Ministry. That is why it is natural for me to praise the work of the ministry, exaggerate it when I can, and hide its shortcomings if I can. In addition, we have posted reports on the results of the ministry's activities for the current 2022 and the past five years on the ministry's website and social media pages, so that those who are interested can read them.

An impartial assessment is given by the prestigious international ratings that evaluate the development of the countries of the world. In particular, the level of innovative development of countries is measured by the Global Innovation Index (GII). GII evaluates the innovative activity of 131 countries according to more than 80 indicators - annual rankings of innovative capabilities and innovative activity of countries are published based on the evaluation criteria developed by the World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO), the French international business school INSEAD and Cornell University.

The global innovation index is divided into several sub-indices, and each of them is further divided into sub-indices. By studying and analyzing these sub-indices, it is determined what aspects should be given importance in the

country's innovation development, mistakes and shortcomings are worked on. That is, the ratings do not just determine the country's position in this or that field, but are an indicator that tells which directions it should pay attention to in its development.

First of all, we should note that Uzbekistan has risen 40 places in this ranking compared to 2015. Currently, our country occupies the 82nd place in this rating, and in the innovative development strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2030, our country aims to be among the 50 best countries in this rating.

The 2022 report of this large-scale study includes an analysis of the scientific and innovative activities of our country. In the same year, experts singled out 3 countries as "global leaders in innovation in 2022" in the cross-section of regions - Uzbekistan was the first among these recognized countries. That is, Uzbekistan became one of the top-3 countries in terms of innovations in the Central and South Asian region after India and Iran.

One of the important indicators of the GII ranking, introduced since 2019, is "Achievement above expectations in the field of innovation", which is compiled annually by GII experts according to the level of income per capita for all four groups of countries. This list includes countries with limited opportunities and high indicators of innovative development, regardless of the level of socio-economic development of the country.

Since 2020, Uzbekistan has been included in this list from the group of countries with below average per capita income. In this regard, summarizing countries with low average income per capita allows to identify the most developing countries in this group. In 2022, for the first time in the history of the GII rating, Uzbekistan entered the top 10 countries with higher than expected achievements in innovative development, regardless of the level of innovation spending per capita.

When we look at the analysis of Uzbekistan's position in the 2022 GII, we can't help but notice that we are significantly behind in the direction of Creative output, that is, we occupy 102nd place. The direction of creativity includes 16 sub-indices, some of which, for example, the intensity of use of intangible assets, brands, national feature films, the entertainment industry and media, information on departments such as relevant international organizations. are not included in the database, but we are currently working on their inclusion by relevant organizations, so we hope that they will be taken into account in the next ranking and our positions will improve.

We also need to work hard on online creativity, for example, while we rank 107th out of 132 countries for creating mobile apps, our activity on GitHub, the largest web service hosting IT projects, is also very low, 104 - we have taken the place.

The most painful part of the creative department for us is the top-level domains section, unfortunately, we rank 132nd in the world in terms of domain usage. In Uzbekistan, a lot of attention is currently being paid to the development of the .uz domain, and sites and information resources are not being organized in global domains such as .com, .net, .org. However, the location of companies, organizations, and scientific institutions in the common zones of the Internet network serves to make investments and develop their exports. In addition to our national domain, the presence of websites of companies and organizations in different domains paves the way for their products to reach world markets. For example, if you search the Volkswagen company on the Internet, you will find the company's sites volkswagen.uz, volkswagen.de. This provides the company with wide penetration into various markets. Among our national brands, the Artel company, Uzbekistan Airways, and the electronic diary site have organized their sites in the .org and .com domains in accordance with global trends in this regard.

Thus, the indicators of innovative development of our country are comprehensive, and for its improvement, development of various fields is required. From the new year, the Ministry of Innovative Development will continue its activities as an agency under the Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation. There is a lot of work ahead - it is necessary to fulfill the tasks defined in the innovative development strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2022-2026. The first of the target indicators of the implementation of this strategy is to improve the position of Uzbekistan in the ranking of the Global Innovation Index.

The state should create favorable conditions for the private sector to implement innovations. This includes measures to encourage the export activity of enterprises or increase the indicators of production efficiency of enterprises (energy saving, labor efficiency, water saving, capital efficiency, etc.). In addition, additional mechanisms should be created to encourage the increase in the size and age of firms, because these are experienced and large firms that have the necessary resources to invest in innovation.

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